

Prioritization of pharmaceutical contaminants in the environment after evaluation of 10 years in-house monitoring data for analytical method upgrade

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In the last years, one of the main concerns about environment contamination has been the presence of the so-called emerging pollutants. In order to monitor these compounds in environmental matrices, including natural and wastewater, specific analytical methodologies need to be developed. The most common applied analytical strategies are the target methodologies, with a preselection of the compounds of interest. However, some of the target compounds can eventually not be detected in the samples while some could remain unspotted. While in the later years non-target and suspect screening methodologies (where no stnds are required), have gained importance in order to cover a broader set of compounds, they can provide only semiquantitative information or tentative identification of the molecules. Thus, to unequivocally identify and measure their concentration in the samples with accuracy, target methodologies are still the best option to be used (in parallel to other ones).

This fact outlines the necessity of a correct prioritization and selection of those compounds of interest and, accordingly, of a regular update of analytical methodologies. In this work, a prioritization to select the most relevant compounds to monitor and characterize water contamination by Pharmaceutical Active Compounds (PhACs) have been carried out. Four main criteria were considered to select the target pollutants starting with their occurrence in wastewater and in the aquatic environment. With that purpose, the findings of the last 10 years of the research group of 123 PhACs in different water matrixes (wastewater, river and sea water) were evaluated. The environmental impact of the micropollutants based on ecotoxicological parameters was also considered. A literature review was performed to obtain values from in vivo toxicology experiments. When no experimental data was available QSAR chemtool was applied (ECOSAR 2.0 software). Finally, bioaccumulation and persistence values were also calculated through ECOSAR 2.0.

Once the most relevant compounds were selected, an upgrade of the existing analytical methodologies was carried out. Compounds that were not usually detected were excluded while new emerging contaminants were added, such as transformation products of some relevant pharmaceutical compounds (e.g. ibuprofen, sulfamethoxazole, metoprolol). The final list comprises 60 compounds. The optimized methodology includes the preconcentration of adequate volumes of each sample type (wastewater, river and sea water) using solid-phase extraction and further analysis by UHPLC-MS/MS. The extraction recoveries were performed at 3 different levels 1, 10 and 100 ppb and satisfactory values were obtained between (33-134%) for most of the compounds. Limits of detection of the overall method ranged from 0.05ng/L to 87 ng/L for the majority of compounds.

To validate this new methodology, 2 sampling campaigns were performed. One in Girona (North East of Spain) and another one in two Greek Islands (Tinos and Lesbos) in 2019-2020. The results proved that the selected compounds were of high relevance since out of the 60 compounds, only 4 were not detected in the water samples. The analgesics were the therapeutic class at higher concentrations, ranging from 39% to 83% of the total concentration of pharmaceutical compounds. Some differences between the countries could be spotted, higher levels of antibiotics, X-ray contrast agents and lipid regulators could be observed in Spain, while the levels of antihypertensives, diuretics, histamine receptor antagonists, psychiatric drugs and β -blockers

were higher in the eastern country. Furthermore, another difference between the zones was the concentration of micropollutants in the river a few kilometers after the wastewater treatment plant, having detected higher values in Spain.

Acknowledgments

This study has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (HYDROUSA, grant agreement N° 776643) and partly supported by the Generalitat de Catalunya (Consolidated Research Groups 2017-SGR-1124, 2017-SGR-1318). S.R.M and G.B. acknowledge the Ramon y Cajal research fellowships (RYC-2014-16707 and RYC-2014-16754) from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness.